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MIRZO ULUGH BEG AND GEOGRAPHY

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Abstract: *This article analyzes ideas concerning the development of geographical knowledge and natural sciences, particularly physical geography, with a focus on mathematical geography and cartography in Central Asia during the era of the eminent astronomer and thinker Ulugh Bek. It also examines the scientific heritage of representatives of the "second Renaissance".*

Keywords: *coordinate, latitude, meridian, sextant, observatory, telescope, astronomical year, globe.*

Introduction. In the 15th century, the individual who elevated Central Asian astronomy to great heights was the enlightened king and naturalist scholar Muhammad Tarag'ay Ulugh Beg (1394-1449). He also made a significant contribution to geography. He established a unique academy of sciences in the city of Samarkand. The academy was the most famous scientific centre in the East at that time, where a whole group of distinguished astronomers led by Ulugh Beg flourished. Among them were Qozizoda Rumi, Mu'iniddin, G'iyosiddin Jamshid, Koshiy, Muhammad Birjandi, Ali Qushchi and others. The Samarkand observatory, which was nurtured by more than 200 scholars gathered around Ulugh Beg, fulfilled this purpose.

The star chart compiled under Ulugh Beg's leadership has served as a reliable beacon for travellers and sailors around the world for 500 years and even today it retains its scientific and practical value in terms of accuracy. Ulugh Beg was a comprehensive scholar, astronomer, geographer, mathematician, historian, philosopher thinker, and a talented statesman. [8]

Main part. Ulugh Beg was born on the 22nd of March 1394 in some sources in Sultaniyyah, Iran. According to Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi in his work "Zafarnama", this event coincides with the "five-year" campaign of the great Amir Timur to Iran and the Near East. When the courier delivered the news of the new guest's birth to the great Amir, Timur's troops were engaged in battle to capture the city of Mardin in northern Iraq. Upon hearing this good news, according to the information provided by

Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, Amir Timur grants safety to the residents of Mardin, waives the tax the citizens were supposed to pay, awards the governorship of the city to Amir Sultan Solih, the brother of the former governor Amir Sultan Isa, and then returns.

The newborn is named Muhammad Taragay at the suggestion of his grandfather Amir Temur. This name was given in honour of Temur's father. However, in history, he is more widely known by the name Ulugh Beg.[12]

The upbringing of Ulugh Beg is overseen by Temur's wife, Saroymulkhanim (Bibikhanim). Davlatshoh Samarqandi highlights that from a young age, Ulugh Beg was exceptionally sharp-minded and presents an instructive story. When Ulugh Beg was just five years old, his grandfather Amir Temur appointed Sheikh Orif Ozariy, the nephew of the palace keeper, as his tutor in 1398. According to Klavikh, Ulugh Beg, who knew five languages: Turkish, Arabic, Persian, Mongolian, and a little Chinese, participated in the ceremonies for receiving his grandfather's foreign ambassadors. In his youth, during his grandfather Amir Temur's travels, Ulugh Beg saw the observatory in Maragheh (near Tehran) and was inspired to vow, "I will build one like that too."

Ulugh Beg distinguished himself in his youth with his works in the fields of mathematics and geography related to astronomy, such as trigonometry and spherical geometry, as well as a general interest in art and intellectual pursuits.

His father, Shah Rukh Mirza, was the governor of Mavarannahr, and after his father's death, he became the sultan of the entire Timurid Empire (1447—1449). During Ulugh Beg's reign, thanks to his attention and patronage, the Timurid Renaissance reached its cultural peak.

Mirzo Ulugh Beg was the ruler of Transoxiana from 1409. He always adhered to the hadith of our Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him), which says, 'Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave.' Ulugh Beg studied the works of Ahmad Fergani, Farabi, Musa Khwarizmi, Biruni, Ibn Sina, and Omar Khayyam. Through these thinkers, he became acquainted with Greek scholars such as Plato, Aristotle, Hipparchus, and Ptolemy. According to Giyasiddin Jamshid Kashi, Ulugh Beg was a wise man who memorised most parts of the Holy Quran. During Ulugh Beg's time, the city of Samarkand thrived even more. Crafts, architecture, literature, and science as a whole flourished in the city, and trade advanced. Davlatshoh Samarqandi wrote in his 'Tazkirat-ush Shuaro': 'The knowledgeable, just, victorious, and generous king Ulugh Beg ascended in the science of the stars to the height of the sky and in the science of meanings, he cut the fabric of knowledge. In his time, the rank of scholars was elevated to the peak.' The unanimous opinion of the distinguished rulers is that throughout the history of Islam, and perhaps from the time of Alexander the Great until now, no scholar and king like Ulugh Beg has sat on the throne of sovereignty.

He administered Samarkand and the Movarounnahr region independently for forty years during the reign of his father Shah Rukh the Great. During this period, Ulugh Beg established madrasas in Bukhara (1417), Samarkand (1420), and Gijduvan (1432-33), as well as charitable institutions in Marv. In these madrasas, in addition to religious sciences, secular sciences were also taught, with more focus on the exact sciences.

Ulugh Beg brought the science and culture of the peoples of Central Asia to the highest level of world science under the conditions of Central Asia. His greatest achievement was establishing the Samarkand scientific school, which served as the academy of that era. More than 200 scholars were active in this scientific school. Among them, the most prominent were Qozizoda Rumi and Ghiyosiddin Jamshid Kashi.

Ulugh Beg gathered prominent scholars of his time and convened a meeting in 1417 dedicated to the construction of an observatory. Regarding the construction of the observatory, Ulugh Beg's contemporary historian Abdurrazzaq Samarkandi wrote about this meeting: "The observatory should be constructed in such a way that it does not tremble or shift over time, and endures for many years to come. For this (construction of the observatory), a suitable location was indicated in the North-East of Samarkand. Until its construction is completed, the following should be carried out: the knowledge of the future staff of the observatory should be improved, additional tables should be prepared, and essential (observation) instruments' components should be made ready...".

Ulugh Beg built one of the largest medieval observatories in the world on the Ko'xak (Cho'ponota) hill near Samarkand in 1428-1429. According to the design of the observatory, it comprised a three-storey circular structure resembling a cave, which contained a marble quadrant with a diameter of 46.4 m and a height of at least 30 m. Its main device was a double-arched passing quadrant that was aligned north to south, resembling a sextant. Through this device, the altitude of celestial bodies was measured as they crossed the celestial meridian. The device was found as a result of excavations and was well preserved in the underground section. Its arc is assumed to be one sixth of a circle with a working part ranging from 20° to 80° . (Figure 1)

The sextant - (from Arabic 'suds', meaning one-sixth of a circle) refers to the instrument that measures the angle between the equator and the ecliptic, allowing for the determination of fundamental astronomical constants such as the annual precession constant, the duration of the tropical year, and others. According to the work 'Ziji Korgoni', this instrument facilitates advancements in the theories of the movements of the Sun, Moon, and planets, enabling high precision in measuring time, which is essential in eclipse theory and practical astronomy. In the observatory, there are small-

sized instruments: armillary sphere, measuring instruments consisting of 2, 4, and 7 rings, triangula, solar and star clocks, astrolabe, and others.

Figure 2

The main 'telescope' of Ulugh Beg's observatory is the sextant.

The quadrant allows for the most accurate recording of the coordinates of light rays at any point in the celestial sphere. Ulugh Beg's scientific works were created thanks to the unique observatory built in Samarkand (Figure 2). The building also had a rich library, as the observatory was not only a place for observation, but also where the strongest scholars - mathematicians, philosophers, and astronomers of that era worked.

Figure 2

The initial appearance of Ulugh Beg's observatory

Mirzo Ulugh Beg's largest astronomical work, 'Ziji Koragoniy', was created in an observatory. 'Ziji jadidi Koragoniy' ('Koragoniy New Astronomical Table') and 'Ulugh Beg ziji' were scientific works created under Mirzo Ulugh Beg's leadership in the observatory near Samarkand in 1437. It consists of two sections (a detailed introduction and a table of 1018 stars given in an elliptical system). The introduction is divided into 4 parts and is described as comprising 4 pages. Of the 430-page Ziji, 60 pages consist of text without tables, while the remaining 370 pages contain astronomical, trigonometrical, geographical, and astrological tables. The Great astronomer's 'Ziji jadidi Koragoniy' is also recorded in historical sources under the names 'Ulugh Beg Ziji', 'Ziji Koragoniy', 'Ziji Sultoni', and others. Its introductory section consists of only 2 pages, discussing the astronomers who participated in the establishment of the observatory and the preparation of the Ziji.

Part 1 discusses the calculations relating to the methods of year counting of Eastern peoples in chronology, the calendars of that time and the transition from one to another. In addition, it provides information on the known calendars of that time and the year numbering system. It covers lunar calendars, Hijri and lunar calendars, the transition from the Solar calendar to the lunar calendar, and the issues of transitioning from one epoch to another. The year counting procedures of Arabs, Greeks, Iranians, Chinese, and Uyghurs, the ways of transitioning from one to another, and the methods of counting their unique national holidays are expressed.

Part 2 is dedicated to spherical and practical astronomy issues. It discusses the determination of the angle between the ecliptic and the equator, methods for finding the coordinates of celestial bodies, establishing the meridian line, determining the Qibla azimuth, finding geographical coordinates, determining the duration of the year, and conducting differential measurements in the celestial sphere.

Table 1

The tilt of the ecliptic to the equator

Erotosfen (e.o.276-194 y.y.)	$23^{\circ}51' 20''$	Error	$+7^{\circ}35''$
Gipparx (II a.)	$23^{\circ}51' 20''$		$+8^{\circ}23''$
Ptolemey (II a)	$23^{\circ}51' 20''$		$+10^{\circ}10''$
Al- Battoniy (tax. 850-929)	$23^{\circ}35'$		$+0^{\circ}17''$
As-Sufiy (903 – 986 yy.)	$23^{\circ}33' 45''$		$+0^{\circ}50''$
Abdul Vafo (940-998)	$23^{\circ}35'$		$+0^{\circ}35''$
Abul-Kuxiy (X asr)	$23^{\circ}51' 01''$		$+16^{\circ}36''$
Ibn Yunus (950 - 1009)	$23^{\circ}34' 52''$		$+0^{\circ}33''$
N. Tusiy (1201 – 1274)	$23^{\circ}30'$		$+2^{\circ}9''$
Ulug'ek (1394 – 1449)	$23^{\circ}30' 17''$		$+0^{\circ}32''$

In part 3, the visible movements of the planets were summarised based on the geocentric system. At that time, information was provided about the movements of the 5 known planets: Saturn, Jupiter, Mars, Venus, and Mercury.

(Table 2)

Coordinates of the planets in 'Ziji Ko`rogoniy'

The name of the planet	According to Ulugh Beg	Currently in account
Zuhal-Saturn	12° 13' 39"	12° 13' 36"
Mushtariy-Yupiter	30° 20' 34"	30° 20' 31"
Mirix_Mars	191° 17' 15"	191° 17' 10"
Zuhro-Venera	224° 17' 32"	224° 17' 30"
Utorud-Merkuriy	53° 43' 13"	53° 43' 3"

The fourth part presents information about the horoscope (from Greek: 'horoskopos' – time observer), focusing primarily on astrology tables. It contains terms related to astrology, points in the celestial sphere, and details about astrological observations. The star chart presented in 'Ziji Ko`rogoniy' was compiled based on observations made in Samarkand. This table ranks second in the history of astronomy after Hipparchus' Ptolemy table (2nd century) in terms of the number of stars and the originality of observations. Many zij, such as 'Ziji Ilhoni' and 'Ziji Hoqoni', were written up until the reign of Mirzo Ulug`bek, as is known from history. Certainly, many scholars have acknowledged the superiority of 'Ziji jadidi Ko`rogoniy' over previous zij. Among the zij created before the invention of optical instruments, 'Ziji Ko`rogoniy' is considered the most complete.

The determination of time and measurement of geographical coordinates, as well as the resolution of various astronomical issues, were practiced in the East and Europe until the 17th century. The star catalogue of "Ziji Khoragoniy" includes 1018 stars, arranged according to constellations similar to Beruni's star catalogue. Only 5% of the 430-page "Ziji Khoragoniy" consists of star tables. It is worth mentioning that the main tasks set by the astronomers of the Samarkand observatory were not, as many thought, to compile a star catalogue, but rather to find the precise values of fundamental astronomical quantities based on systematic observations of the Sun, Moon, and planets (including Mercury, Venus, Mars, Jupiter, and Saturn), such as the obliquity of the ecliptic to the equator, annual procession, the length of the stellar year, and several other astronomical quantities. About 80 per cent of the tables of "Ziji Ko`rogoniy" are dedicated to the Sun, Moon, and five planets.

The work also contains other tables. A table that includes geographical coordinates for 570 points has been compiled mainly using various sources: in the Beruni table, geographical points are given in a 'climatic' order starting from the equator, while in the Ulugh Beg table, geographical points are based primarily on the principle from west to east, originating from the Azores Islands, considered the farthest western part of the European continent (Figure 3). However, the descriptions of cities in both tables are similar (Table 3).

Table 3

Table of geographic coordinates in the works of Beruni and Ulugh Beg

In the Beruni table	Ulugh Beg's table
Qulzum - a city on the edge of the Red Sea, this sea is also famously known as the Suf sea	Qulzum - by the seaside
Ramla - a small city in Palestine	Ramla - from Palestine
Qibris - an island in the Mediterranean Sea	Qibrit
Trabzunda - a port in Rumia. On the shores of the Buntus sea.	Trabzond
Bob al-Abvob – famous as Darbandi Khasaron; by the sea	Bab al-Abwob
Bokuyya – a place where white oil (petroleum) comes out	Bokuyya
Kot (the second city of Khorezm), on the eastern side of Jayhun	Kot
Constantinople – between the Rum and the Bontus Sea, on the Gulf coast	Constantinople
The city of Xazar – ruins on the bank of the Atil River	Khazar city

Figure 3

The map of the prime meridians accepted by medieval scholars

The trigonometric tables of sines and tangents were calculated using new methods developed by Samarkand scholars; they are much more accurate compared to the tables calculated up to that time.

"Zij-i Khuragoni" is written in Persian; later, it was translated into Arabic and Turkish. Ulugh Beg's student Ali Qushji made a significant contribution to the widespread distribution of the Zij manuscripts. "Zij-i Khuragoni" was first published in Europe in 1648 (England); subsequently, it was translated into many European languages. Hand-copied versions of "Zij-i Khuragoni" are preserved in libraries in England, France, Turkey, and India, with one of the oldest copies written in Persian kept at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences.[2]

"In the preface of the 'Zij-i Ko'ragoniy': 'We have resolved the matter of observing the illuminators. We carried this out in collaboration with Qozizoda Rumiyy and G'iyosiddin Jamshid... In this, the important work of writing and formalising the

'Zij' was led by G'iyosiddin, and later Qozizoda Rumiyy passed away. After that, the formalisation of the work until the end was completed together with Ulugh Beg's son Ali ibn Muhammad Qushchi.' The observation of the movement of stars, carried out continuously for more than twenty years, as cited in some sources, resulted in 'Ulugh Beg's zij', considered the most perfect until the optical instruments were discovered in the 17th century.

The positions and states of 1018 stars in the ecliptic system, the length of the year (365 days, 6 hours, 10 minutes, 58 seconds), and the tilt of the Earth's axis (23.52) have been determined. This was considered a monumental scientific leap for its time and laid the foundation for the development of both Eastern and Western astronomy in the following centuries. The work 'Zij-i Jadid-i Khoragoniy' states: 'We have determined the positions of the stars listed in our catalogue relative to the beginning of the year 841 in the Hijri calendar. However, taking into account that their correct ascension has advanced by 1 degree for every 70 solar years, it is possible to accurately find the position of each of them at any given time.' [2]

Among the scholars of astronomy, the most knowledgeable was Giyosiddin Jamshid, who managed to obtain a value equal to $230^{\circ} 30' 17''$ at the Samarkand observatory. The value determined during Ulugh Beg's time corresponds to $230^{\circ} 30' 49''$. Therefore, the error of the Samarkand scholars in this matter amounted to only 32 arcs seconds, which is considered very high precision.

The director of the Tashkent Astronomical Observatory, Academician V.P. Shcheglov wrote about this mistake: "During Ulugh Beg's era, the instrument was precisely installed along the meridian, and perhaps due to changes in the plane of the instrument over five centuries, various events (earthquakes, the instrument's subsidence, and so on - M.M.) may have caused the deformation of the device. It should be noted that the meridian direction for the sextant at the Ulugh Beg Observatory is the only and ancient device on Earth that was found with the highest level of accuracy for that period."

Ancient peoples associated constellations with various images linked to a particular people's economic activities, culture, or religious ideas. Different peoples had different boundaries and names for constellations. The Greek-Latin variant of the names of these constellations, based on the rich mythology of these peoples, gained predominant importance in astronomy. However, by the end of the Middle Ages and in the present day, not all the names currently in use are related to this mythology. Some were named by ancient peoples, while others received their names later.

Figure 4

In conclusion, it can be said that two major works of Ulugh Beg have reached us, the first being 'Tarixi arba` ulus', which provides extensive information about the political life and history of the territories conquered by Genghis Khan. The second book, 'Ziji Ko`rogoniy', was initiated by Ulugh Beg and completed by his talented student Ali Qushji, and is considered a high example of medieval astronomy. This work consists of astronomical observations and mathematical calculations, and its geographical and cartographic significance lies primarily in the fact that it calculates the coordinates of 570 geographical points on the Earth's surface, indicating that 'Ziji Ko`rogon' is not only an astronomical table but also a geographical one.

Ulugh Beg's rich scientific heritage confirms how high a scholar he was. The genius of creative thought has made an invaluable contribution to the development of human knowledge and civilisation. Thus, centuries later, the name of Ulugh Beg remains a symbol that unites both Eastern and Western peoples in their pursuit of noble goals.

The high spiritual and significant scientific legacy of Mirzo Ulugh Beg is currently being studied at the leading higher education institutions and research centres around the world.

Ulugh Beg's life path is also of significant importance in awakening the geographical thinking of students. Below, we attempted to develop a geographical map

along the routes taken by Ulugh Beg, who ruled over an area of more than 10 million km² that included the continents of Eurasia and Africa during that time. It is a fact that understanding the history, geography, peoples, their economic activities and economies of these regions required being both a strong geographer and cartographer. (Figure 5)

Figure 5

The map of Mirzo Ulugh Beg's life path

The map was created by the author.

Ulugh Beg's geographical legacy:

- Determining the coordinates of the local area;
- Establishing the angle of intersection of the large circle that indicates the qibla direction with the local meridian;
- Knowing trigonometric calculation rules and methods for calculating geographic coordinates;
- Determining the altitude of the Sun based on geographic coordinates;
- Creating measuring instruments that indicate different times;
- The "Ziji Ko'ragoniy" contains the coordinates of 247 cities and populated areas.- According to calculations made in 1437, the incline of the ecliptic is equal to 23°30'17" and this value differs by only 0'32" from modern calculations;

- One astronomical year calculated by Ulugh Beg is equal to 365 days, 6 hours, 10 minutes, and 8 seconds, which differs by only 58 seconds from current data;
- The star catalogue of "Ziji Ko'ragoniy" includes 1018 stars.- Ulugh Beg constructed a sundial in Samarkand with a height of 50 metres.

In 1994, the 600th anniversary of the scholar was celebrated internationally, with various events attended by foreign scholars, specialists, and public figures; in 2009, an international scientific conference dedicated to the 615th anniversary of Mirzo Ulugh Beg's birth took place in Paris. The ongoing events clearly demonstrate the immense global interest in Mirzo Ulugh Beg's scientific and spiritual heritage.

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